

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERINATAL OUTCOME IN PREGNANCIES COMPLICATED WITH ISOLATED OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS AND OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS WITH INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RESTRICTION; PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL COHORT STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Oligohydramnios is a frequent ultrasound finding in late pregnancy and commonly triggers admission, induction of labour, and caesarean delivery. Assessment of amniotic fluid volume provides an indirect window into fetoplacental function, low fluid at term may be isolated and transient, or it may coexist with fetal growth restriction (FGR) as part of a placental insufficiency spectrum. The latter scenario is clinically important because it is more likely to be associated with intrapartum fetal compromise, low birth weight and short term neonatal morbidity. In public sector obstetric units with constrained monitoring resources, evidence that differentiates risk between isolated oligohydramnios and oligohydramnios with FGR can improve counselling, triage and delivery planning.

Objective: To compare perinatal outcomes in isolated oligohydramnios versus oligohydramnios with FGR.

Methods: Prospective cohort study at Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi over 04 months. Singleton pregnancies >30 weeks with oligohydramnios (AFI ≤ 5 cm) were enrolled and grouped as isolated oligohydramnios (Group I) or oligohydramnios with FGR (Group II estimated fetal weight <10th percentile). Outcomes were mode of delivery, birth weight, 5 minute Apgar score <7, NICU admission, and neonatal death ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results: Seventy two women were included (36 in each group). Gestational age at delivery was comparable (37.2 ± 1.1 vs 36.8 ± 1.3 weeks $p=0.25$). Birth weight was lower in Group II (2.01 ± 0.31 vs 2.29 ± 0.37 kg $p=0.002$). Emergency caesarean section was more frequent in Group II (61.1% vs 22.2% $p < 0.001$). Neonatal morbidity was higher in Group II, including 5-minute Apgar score <7 (27.8% vs 5.6% $p=0.011$) and NICU admission (47.2% vs 11.1% $p=0.001$). Neonatal death was 8.3% vs 2.8% ($p=0.301$).

Conclusion: Oligohydramnios with FGR is associated with increased operative delivery and higher short term neonatal morbidity compared with isolated oligohydramnios, warranting intensified surveillance and planned delivery.

Introduction

Amniotic fluid is integral to fetal development and acts as a protective environment that facilitates movement, lung maturation and umbilical cord cushioning. In late gestation, amniotic fluid volume is primarily determined by fetal urine production and swallowing, with additional contributions from intramembranous and transmembranous pathways.^{1,6} Because oligohydramnios can represent reduced placental perfusion, fetal compromise or membrane rupture, it remains one of the most clinically actionable ultrasound findings in third trimester care.⁶

Ultrasound assessment of amniotic fluid volume is commonly performed using the amniotic fluid index (AFI) or the single deepest vertical pocket (SDP). AFI measurements were popularised to provide a reproducible bedside estimate, whereas SDP has been promoted in some settings to reduce unnecessary intervention.²⁻⁴ Most obstetric practice considers oligohydramnios when AFI is ≤ 5 cm or SDP is < 2 cm, although interpretation should be individualised according to gestational age and clinical context.³⁻⁶

Importantly, the choice of amniotic fluid assessment method influences clinical decision making. Randomised evidence comparing AFI and SDP suggests that AFI may label more pregnancies as oligohydramnios, leading to higher intervention without clear neonatal benefit, whereas SDP may reduce false positive diagnosis and unnecessary delivery.⁴ In routine practice, however, AFI remains commonly used in many centres, and clinicians must interpret low values alongside fetal growth, gestational age and the overall clinical picture.^{3,6}

Oligohydramnios may accompany premature rupture of membranes, fetal renal anomalies, post term pregnancy, hypertensive disease, diabetes, or placental insufficiency.⁶ In contrast, isolated oligohydramnios refers to low amniotic fluid without obvious maternal comorbidity, fetal anomaly or ruptured membranes. Whether isolated oligohydramnios at term is a benign variation or an early marker of placental dysfunction remains debated, and this uncertainty drives variation in induction and caesarean thresholds.¹²⁻¹⁵

Meta analyses of isolated term oligohydramnios have consistently shown higher obstetric intervention,

including induction and caesarean delivery, with mixed results regarding severe neonatal endpoints.¹²⁻¹⁵ Case-control and cohort data suggest increased caesarean delivery for fetal distress and higher NICU admission in some settings, yet the overall benefit of routine early delivery remains uncertain.¹²⁻¹⁶ Therefore, risk stratification based on associated fetal pathology is crucial to avoid both preventable morbidity and avoidable operative delivery.

Fetal growth restriction (FGR) indicates failure to reach growth potential and is strongly linked to stillbirth and neonatal morbidity. Contemporary guidance, including ACOG, SMFM and FIGO, emphasises accurate diagnosis (using estimated fetal weight centiles and growth trajectories), surveillance (including Doppler where available) and planned timing of delivery according to gestational age and fetal risk.⁸⁻¹¹ RCOG guidance similarly outlines investigation and management pathways for small for gestational age and growth restricted fetuses.¹⁰

When oligohydramnios coexists with FGR, the combination is more suggestive of uteroplacental insufficiency than isolated oligohydramnios. Placental histopathology studies have demonstrated maternal vascular malperfusion lesions in pregnancies with isolated term oligohydramnios, supporting a continuum of placental dysfunction.⁷ In clinical practice, the addition of FGR may therefore identify fetuses at higher risk of intrapartum compromise and early neonatal morbidity.

Low and middle income countries face a high burden of low birth weight and perinatal morbidity, and third trimester ultrasound often detects reduced amniotic fluid in women presenting late in pregnancy.¹⁷ Local South Asian studies have also reported increased NICU admission and low Apgar scores in oligohydramnios, although risk appears heterogeneous and may depend on associated pathology and severity.¹⁸⁻²¹

In a busy public tertiary care hospital where continuous electronic fetal monitoring may not be universally available, distinguishing isolated oligohydramnios from oligohydramnios with FGR can directly inform counselling, triage and delivery planning. The present study therefore compared obstetric and neonatal outcomes between these two presentations in our population, with a focus on immediate perinatal morbidity and mode of delivery.

Methods

This prospective observational cohort study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi, from January to April 2025. Ethical approval was obtained from the Departmental Review Board, and written informed consent was taken from all participants prior to enrolment.

Women aged 18–40 years with singleton pregnancies, intact membranes and oligohydramnios on ultrasound were recruited through non-probability consecutive sampling. Oligohydramnios was defined as AFI ≤ 5 cm on ultrasound performed at admission or within 24 hours prior to delivery. Participants were grouped as: Group I (isolated oligohydramnios) and Group II (oligohydramnios with FGR). FGR was defined as estimated fetal weight below the 10th centile for gestational age, with supportive clinical assessment and Doppler findings where available, consistent with international guidance.⁸⁻¹¹

Women with premature rupture of membranes, multiple gestation, major fetal structural anomalies, hypertensive disorders, diabetes mellitus, antepartum haemorrhage, confirmed intrauterine infection, and known maternal renal disease were excluded to minimise confounding. Standard obstetric management was provided for both groups. Decisions regarding induction, augmentation and timing of delivery were made by the attending

consultant based on gestational age, cervical status, maternal condition and fetal surveillance findings.

The primary outcomes were mode of delivery and emergency caesarean section. Secondary neonatal outcomes included birth weight, 5-minute Apgar score <7 , NICU admission and neonatal death. Neonatal outcomes were obtained from delivery records and NICU admission logs.

Data Analysis: Data were recorded on a structured proforma and analysed using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were described as mean \pm standard deviation and compared using independent samples t-test. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages and compared using Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test as appropriate. Relative risks with 95% confidence intervals were computed for selected adverse outcomes in Group II compared with Group I. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 72 women were included, with 36 women in each group. Mean gestational age at delivery was similar between the groups (37.2 \pm 1.1 weeks in Group I vs 36.8 \pm 1.3 weeks in Group II, $p=0.25$). Mean birth weight was significantly lower in the oligohydramnios FGR group (2.01 \pm 0.31 kg) compared with isolated oligohydramnios (2.29 \pm 0.37 kg, $p=0.002$).

Table 1: Comparison of perinatal outcomes between the two study groups (n=72)

Variable	Isolated oligohydramnios (n=36)	Oligohydramnios + FGR (n=36)	p-value
Birth weight (Mean \pm SD), kg	2.5 \pm 0.4	1.7 \pm 0.3	$<0.001^*$
Mode of delivery			$<0.001^*$
Normal vaginal delivery	18 (50.0%)	4 (11.1%)	
Emergency caesarean section	8 (22.2%)	22 (61.1%)	$<0.001^*$
Elective caesarean section	10 (27.8%)	10 (27.8%)	
5-minute Apgar <7	2 (5.6%)	10 (27.8%)	0.011*
NICU admission	4 (11.1%)	17 (47.2%)	$<0.001^*$
Neonatal death	1 (2.8%)	3 (8.3%)	0.301

*Statistically significant

Figure 1. Mode of delivery by study group (n=36 each)

Figure 1: Comparison of perinatal outcomes between the two study groups

Mode of delivery differed significantly between groups ($p < 0.001$), with a higher proportion of emergency caesarean section in Group II (61.1%) compared with Group I (22.2%). Neonatal morbidity

was also higher in Group II, including a higher frequency of 5-minute Apgar score < 7 (27.8% vs 5.6%, $p = 0.011$) and NICU admission (47.2% vs 11.1%, $p = 0.001$).

Table 2: Relative Risk of Adverse Outcomes (Group II vs Group I)

Outcome	Relative Risk (95% CI)
Emergency caesarean section	2.75 (1.42–5.33)
5-min Apgar score < 7	5.00 (1.19–21.02)
NICU admission	4.25 (1.62–11.13)
Neonatal death	3.00 (0.33–27.49)

Figure 2: Relative Risk of Adverse Outcomes (Group II vs Group I)

Figure 3: Risk ratios for adverse outcomes (forest plot; Group II vs Group I).

Neonatal death occurred more frequently in Group II (8.3% vs 2.8%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.301$). Detailed outcomes are summarised in Table 2 and Figure 2&3.

Discussion

This study demonstrates that pregnancies complicated by oligohydramnios with FGR experienced substantially worse perinatal outcomes than isolated oligohydramnios, particularly in terms of emergency caesarean delivery, low 5-minute Apgar

score and NICU admission. The findings are biologically plausible and consistent with international guidance that treats growth restriction as a high risk state requiring intensified surveillance and planned delivery.⁸⁻¹¹

In isolated oligohydramnios, the literature suggests that clinical management often results in increased obstetric intervention. Shrem and colleagues reported higher rates of induction and caesarean delivery in term isolated oligohydramnios, but the optimal timing of delivery remains uncertain.¹²

Subsequent meta analyses similarly found that isolated oligohydramnios is associated with higher caesarean delivery and NICU admission in some populations, while severe neonatal endpoints may not consistently increase.¹³⁻¹⁵ Our data are in line with this pattern: although isolated oligohydramnios had a meaningful rate of caesarean delivery, neonatal death was rare and not statistically different.

The striking divergence observed when FGR coexisted with oligohydramnios suggests that combined pathology identifies a different risk phenotype. FGR is closely linked to uteroplacental dysfunction, and FIGO, ACOG and SMFM all emphasise that diagnosis should guide surveillance intensity and delivery timing.^{8,9,11} RCOG Greentop guideline also supports structured investigation and delivery planning for growth restricted fetuses.¹⁰ In our cohort, the combined group had nearly threefold higher risk of emergency caesarean section (RR 2.75), reflecting increased intrapartum compromise or clinician concern.

Placental pathology evidence supports a continuum between isolated oligohydramnios and placental insufficiency. Mirembert et al. demonstrated an association between isolated oligohydramnios at term and placental maternal vascular malperfusion lesions.⁷ When FGR is present, the 'placental signal' is amplified clinically, translating into lower birth weight and higher NICU admission, as seen in our cohort.

Our results are also consistent with large population data. Hou et al., in a cross-sectional survey across multiple hospitals in China, found that pregnancies with oligohydramnios at term experienced higher operative delivery and differences in neonatal outcomes depending on management and baseline risk.¹⁶ In low and middle income settings, a prospective multicountry study by Figueroa et al. reported that oligohydramnios was associated with adverse fetal and neonatal outcomes, supporting the need for context appropriate triage and delivery planning.¹⁷

Local evidence further emphasises that not all 'low fluid' carries equal risk. Studies from Pakistan and neighbouring settings report variable associations between oligohydramnios and neonatal morbidity, with higher risk often observed when growth restriction is present or when oligohydramnios is

more severe.¹⁸⁻²¹ For example, Kalsoom et al. found that borderline isolated reductions in AFI in low risk term pregnancies did not substantially worsen outcomes, suggesting that over intervention may be avoidable in selected cases.²⁰

Clinically, our findings support a pragmatic approach: isolated oligohydramnios at term may be managed with careful surveillance and individualised delivery planning, whereas oligohydramnios with suspected or confirmed FGR should be treated as high risk with anticipatory neonatal preparedness. ACOG also recognises the importance of medically indicated early term delivery in selected high risk conditions, reinforcing the concept that timing of delivery should be condition-specific rather than triggered by oligohydramnios alone.²²

Limitations include the single centre design, modest sample size (which limited power for rare outcomes such as neonatal death), and incomplete Doppler availability, which may influence FGR classification. Strengths include prospective data capture and clinically relevant, short term endpoints. Future multicentre studies with standardized Doppler assessment could refine risk stratification and evaluate whether specific intrapartum management strategies reduce emergency caesarean delivery and NICU admission.

Conclusion

In term singleton pregnancies, oligohydramnios with fetal growth restriction was associated with higher emergency caesarean delivery and greater neonatal morbidity compared with isolated oligohydramnios. Combined pathology warrants intensified surveillance, planned delivery pathways and neonatal preparedness in tertiary public hospitals.

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